

ANALYSES ON DYNAMIC STRESS-STRAIN AND MICROCRACKING IN FIBER REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical analyses have been made on the characteristics of stress-strain under cyclic loading in fiber reinforced MMC and, a stress-strain model in micro-site of material was built up. The cyclically loading equations under tension-compression were derived out, too. According to this model cyclic deformation characteristics were classified, and the processes and factors of mechanics hardening or softening and physics hardening or softening were analysed and discussed. Analytical calculations were made in the light of mechanics on the microcrack initiating condition and patterns of the different type of composite materials.

KEY WORDS: fiber reinforced metal matrix composite, cyclic loading equation, mechanics and physics hardening/softening

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the divergence of properties between matrix and reinforcement in composite materials, in the processes of cyclic loading it should take place that the entirely different stress-strain behaviors from static loading, as well as the crack initiating positions and patterns [1, 2]. Also, through the interface between matrix and fiber the divided stresses will transfer as the cycle proceeds. Such transference will directly influence the deformation character of matrix and reinforcement as well as the crack initiating sites.

2. DYNAMIC STRESS-STRAIN ANALYSES IN MICROSITES OF MMC

2.1 Dynamic stress-strain model in microsites under cyclic loading

The analytical unit of fiber reinforced MMC is shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 is an analytical model which is designed from iso-strain assumption in the cyclically loading processes. The abscissa σ_1 in it is the divided stress in matrix acted by external load $p(\sigma)$, and the ordinate σ_2 is the divided stress in reinforcement (fiber). The curve $oab'o''b''$ is the loading track which represents the relative change in divided stresses in the matrix and fiber during a stress circle. $o'o''$ stands for the null load track, and

the line p-p, p'-p' are the load equilibrium line whose slope is related on the fiber volume fraction. σ_1 and σ_{2r} are the residual stresses in constituents after unloading.

2.2 Divided stress transfer and expressions of cyclic residual strain

According to above analytical model it can be derived the "loading equation" of divided stress transference between matrix and fiber in different stage of deformation:

$$\sigma_2^{(n)} = \begin{cases} \sigma_1^{(n)} = \sigma(\text{or } p) & (\text{whole elastic}) \\ (-1)^{(n-1)} [E_{0.2} \epsilon_{0.2} \left| \frac{\sigma_1^{(n)} - \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}}{\sigma_{1s}^{(n)} - \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}} \right|^{\frac{1}{m_1}} - D\sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}] & (\text{matrix yield}) \\ (-1) [K_2 \epsilon_{0.2} m_2 \left| \frac{\sigma_1^{(n)} - \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}}{\sigma_{1s}^{(n)} - \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}} \right|^{\frac{m_1}{m_2}} - D\sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}] & (\text{both yield}) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

If the opposite yield can not appear during cyclic unloading processes, after each cyclic unloading the residual strain $\epsilon_r^{(n)}$ can be expressed as:

$$\epsilon_r^{(n)} = \begin{cases} 0 & (\text{whole elastic}) \\ (-1)^{n-1} [\epsilon_{0.2} \left| \frac{\sigma_1^{(n)} - \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}}{\sigma_{1s}^{(n)} - \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}} \right|^{\frac{1}{m_1}} - \frac{1}{E_2} (D\sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)} + \sigma)] & (\text{matrix yield}) \\ (-1)^{n-1} \left\{ [\epsilon_{0.2} \left| \frac{\sigma_1^{(n)} - \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}}{\sigma_{1s}^{(n)} - \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}} \right|^{\frac{m_1}{m_2}} - \frac{D}{K_2} \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)}]^{\frac{1}{m_2}} - \frac{\sigma}{E_2} \right\} & (\text{both yield}) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$\sigma_{1s}^{(n)} = [\sigma_{1s}^{\frac{1}{m_1}} + \sigma_{1r}^{(n-1)\frac{1}{m_1}}]^{m_1} \quad (3)$$

and $\sigma_i^{(n)}$ mean the divided stresses in load circulation, m_i the deformation hardening indexes, $E_2(K_2)$ the Young's modulus of fiber, $\sigma_{ir}^{(n)}$ the cyclic residual stresses, $\sigma_1, \sigma_{1s}^{(n)}$ the matrix original and cyclic yield stress, respectively, $\epsilon_{0.2}$ the yield strain of the matrix and N the cycle number, $n = \frac{1}{2}N$. When the cyclic number is equal to N cyclic plastic strain amplitude can be written as:

$$\Delta \epsilon_p^{(N)} = \epsilon_p^{(n)} - \epsilon_p^{(n-1)} \quad (4)$$

Equations (1) and (3) are called "cyclically loading equations" which describes the relationships among cyclic number N , alternating external load σ (or p) and divided stresses σ_1, σ_2 . One can use equation (2) to calculate the residual plastic strain range $\Delta \epsilon_p^{(N)}$ during circulation of load.

3. DEFORMATION CHARACTERISTIC ANALYSES DURING LOAD ALTERNATING

3.1 Classification of cyclic deformation characteristics

On the basis of the change in divided stresses and strains during loading cycling processes the cyclic deformation characteristic in local site can be divided into four basic patterns (shown in Fig. 3):

Type A: cyclically shift-up positive creep ($\frac{d\epsilon_r^+(N)}{dN} > 0, \frac{d\epsilon_r^-(N)}{dN} > 0$);

Type B: cyclically shift-down negative creep ($\frac{d\epsilon_r^+(N)}{dN} < 0, \frac{d\epsilon_r^-(N)}{dN} < 0$);

These two types of cyclic deformation can further separate into hardening ($\frac{d\Delta \epsilon_r}{dN} < 0$) and softening ($\frac{d\Delta \epsilon_r}{dN} > 0$) modes in the light of relative changes in $\frac{d\epsilon_r^+(N)}{dN}$ and $\frac{d\epsilon_r^-(N)}{dN}$.

Type C: face-to-face shrinkage $\frac{d\epsilon_r^+(N)}{dN} < 0, \frac{d\epsilon_r^-(N)}{dN} > 0$, typical cyclic hardening mode);

Type D: bank-to-bank expansion $\frac{d\epsilon_r^+(N)}{dN} > 0, \frac{d\epsilon_r^-(N)}{dN} < 0$, typical cyclic softening mode).

The four basic modes mentioned above reflect the relative changing situations in divided stresses and residual strains during load alternating.

3. 2 Influencing factors in cyclic deformation processes

According to the property feature of matrix in MMC, the cyclic "hardening" or "softening" processes that are similar to normal metals would take place in cyclic deformations. The difference from single phase alloy is that this behavior may practically consist of two basic processes: mechanics hardening or softening and physics hardening or softening processes. What is called mechanics hardening or softening indicates such a phenomenon that the residual strain range resulted by divided stress transference increases or decreases each cycle, while the physics hardening or softening is another different phenomenon of alloy phase strengthening and weakening resulted by the change in dislocation density and its structure of constituents (chiefly matrix) during cyclic deformation processes. The two processes are chiefly controlled by following factors:

1) Stress level and load pattern: The stress level directly influences the value of residual stress $\sigma_r^{(n)}$ between matrix and fiber after every cyclic unloading, thereby influencing the shape and position of the loading curve and causing the strain extent to expand or shrink.

2) Microstructure state of matrix: Experiments had demonstrated that the higher the dislocation density (before cyclic loading), the greater the cyclic softening rate and degree are, but the matrix with low dislocation density normally behaves cyclic hardening characteristic [2]

3) Distribution and fraction of reinforcing fibers: The fiber volume fraction essentially effects the slope D of loading equilibrium line p-p' (or p'-p', Fig. 2). From Fig. 2 and equation (1) it can be found that the greater the D value, the higher the residual strain range $\Delta\epsilon_r^{(N)}$ is after loading then unloading, and so, the cyclic stable residual strain range $\Delta\epsilon_w$ is higher.

4) Residual stresses: In the production treatment of MMC residual stresses in the constituents are sure to be induced, as a result, the difference in physic parameters (such as CTE, young's modulus E, poisson ratio etc.) of matrix and reinforcement consequently make the initial position and slope of loading curve effected, so that the cyclic deformation feature is changed.

4. MICROCRACK INITIATING POSITION PATTERNS ANALYSES

4. 1 Cyclic deformation type A

Because $\frac{d\sigma_2^+(N)}{dN} > 0, \frac{d\sigma_1^+(N)}{dN} < 0$ during circulation the divided stress $\sigma_2^+(N)$ in fiber increases each cycle, though the divided stress $\sigma_1^+(N)$ in matrix decreases. Thereby if the interfacial bonding is strong, the fiber will fail earlier than matrix when $\sigma_2^+(N) = \sigma_k$, and the crack initiation number Nf will be reduced as the fiber volume fraction matrix yield strength and hardening index decrease. Whereas if the interface is weak and the interfacial chemical compound is brittle the crack initiation will occur first here, consequently leading fibers to fail. Thus Nf will drop with the increase in the interfacial compound thickness δ . When δ reaches its critical value δ_c the fiber and interfacial compound fracture in the same time (transverse fracture). On the other hand, if the difference of the matrix and fiber poisson is great and if the "dynamic weakening" in interface causes the interfacial strength to decrease, the longitudinal crack initiation will take place in the interface.

4. 2 Cyclic deformation type B

In this situation the crack initiation pattern and position in microsites are chiefly related with the stress state and the properties of matrix. Because $\frac{d\sigma_1^+(N)}{dN}$ is positive and increases with the increasing fiber volume fraction and matrix hardening index m_1 so that the crack initiation generally appears in matrix first (transverse fracture). If cyclic strain value (shift-down) is great, the loading in compression-half-cycle should cause the fiber to crack.

4. 3 Cyclic deformation C

The cracking patterns in this type of deformation are the combination of the above two modes (in type A and B), that could be particularly analysed from the situations among external load and properties of the constituents.

4. 4 Cyclic deformation D

Owing to divided stress $\sigma_2^{(n)}$ and cyclic residual strain $\epsilon_r^{(n)}$ decreasing with cycling this type of cyclic deformation pattern must be optimum only in view point of stresses.

5. CONCLUSIONS

5. 1 The loading equation is derived as equation (1) for the fiber reinforced MMC and the residual strain is determined by equation(2).
5. 2 The matrix is subjected to mechanics and physics hardening or softening depended on the external stress level, matrix original microstructure state, fiber distribution and residual stresses.
5. 3 The microcracking initiation and patterns for the different cyclic deformation modes are not the same in mechanics view point.

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Fig. 1 Analytical model of divided stresses

Fig. 2 Schematic of dynamic double-stress Model

Fig. 3 Schematic of dynamic stress-strain modes

- (A) Face-to-face shrinking mode
- (B) Bank-to-bank expanding mode
- (C) Co-direction shift-up mode
- (D) Co-direction shift-down mode